

SURVEILLANCE CARD_CCHF_2_wild ruminants

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Serological surveillance of wild ruminants in high-risk areas.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen. Early detection of a change of the geographic distribution/spread to new areas.
3	Target species and group	All wild ruminant species in a high-risk area.
4	Target sector / production type	Hunted wild ruminants, or wild ruminants found dead.
5	Geographical area covered	High-risk areas with regards to introduction of disease (close to endemic areas) and presence of ticks (climate, vegetation). Areas with suspected presence of CCHF or which have previously been endemic to CCHF.
6	Age group	Adult animals.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Hunted wild ruminants, or wild ruminants found dead.
8	Sampling time period	Vector period (spring to autumn).
9	Sampling matrix	Blood serum.
10	Type of disease indicators	Presence of antibodies.
11	Sampling unit	Individual animal.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	All animals hunted or found dead in the region (if it is possible to collect serum).
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Indirect immunofluorescence test or ELISA. Pooling of samples from the same herd is possible, but currently no information on sensitivity of tests on pooled samples is

		available. Standardization of serological test is needed, because currently no method is accepted as gold standard methodology.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The component contributes to case detection and possibly to compare relative risks across geographical areas, but as this is a biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population (convenience sampling) it cannot be used directly to estimate the system sensitivity.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Q-Fever serology.
18	References	<p>1) Cicculi V, Maitre A, Ayhan N, Mondoloni S, Paoli JC, Vial L, de Lamballerie XN, Charrel R, Falchi A. Lack of Evidence for Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever Virus in Ticks Collected from Animals, Corsica, France. <i>Emerg Infect Dis.</i> 2022 May;28(5):1035-1038. doi: 10.3201/eid2805.211996. PMID: 35447051; PMCID: PMC9045455.</p> <p>2) Mazzola LT, Kelly-Cirino C. Diagnostic tests for Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever: a widespread tickborne disease. <i>BMJ Glob Health.</i> 2019 Feb 20;4(Suppl 2):e001114. doi: 10.1136/bmjgh-2018-001114. PMID: 30899574; PMCID: PMC6407549.</p>